

PREPARATION OF SOCIAL PEDAGOGY STUDENTS FOR THE PROFESSION IN THE CURRENT PERIOD

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the professional training of future social pedagogy teachers (social teachers) is one of the urgent tasks of teaching students in the direction of social pedagogy at the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences. Modern pedagogical technologies are used in teaching students in this direction.

Based on the results of the research aimed at presenting the professional characteristics of the students of the Faculty of Social Pedagogy, we propose to introduce innovations in the current curricula to the study program of Information Technologies in Education and thereby strengthen the independence of the profession, which has experienced a unique development in our country.

Keywords: *social pedagogy, professional characteristics of students of social pedagogy, curricula, professional identity*

In addition to the study of the professional characteristics of students, an analysis of the "TAT" science curriculum was carried out to create a constructive proposal for innovations in the curriculum subjects.

The curriculum should not only meet the current requirements of the higher education institution (marketing of services), but also be adapted to the professional identity of future social pedagogues and the development of students' competencies.

The term profession refers to a specific occupation based on a long theoretical training that forms the basis of professional activity. The associated social role forms a complex unity of some kind of professional culture with this profession.

A social teacher cannot be defined clearly and simply (for example, the profession of a teacher). A social worker works in many places and in different disciplines. The school(s) does not have its time constants or standardized templates (for example: curriculum, educational program, etc.). The profession may be closely related to the profession of teacher or therapist, but it certainly cannot replace it.

With the increase in risky behavior in our society, the profession of social worker is becoming a necessity. Therefore, universities prepare students in the social sphere.

Pedagogical programs are consistent with continuous and long-term training and aim to stimulate the need for lifelong learning. The profession of a social teacher requires comprehensiveness.

What are the professional characteristics of social pedagogy students? We asked ourselves this research question to explore the professional identity of the social educator. Since we cannot actually observe the work of a social pedagogue, we must focus on individuals who are currently undergoing professional training for social educators. We elaborate on the main research question in several sub-research questions:

- What is the professional direction of social pedagogy students?
- What are their professional skills and qualifications?
- What is the behavior of students of social pedagogy?
- What is the psychological profile of social pedagogy students?
- What is the concept of the "Social Pedagogy" curriculum at the Faculty of Humanities?

The main purpose of the study is to determine the professional characteristics of the students and thus develop recommendations for their future professions.

Questionnaires were conducted on these recommendations.

Several universities of European countries participated in these studies, and many universities teaching social pedagogy organized seminar trainings. These are: South Czech University in České Budějovice, Masaryk University in Brno, University of Ostrava in Ostrava, University of Hradec Kralove, Jan Evangelista Purkyně University

in Ústí nad Labem, Charles University in Prague, Palacki University in Olomouc, Thomas Bata University in Zlin. One of these universities was randomly selected for complex analysis.

The main research group consists of 166 students in the field of social pedagogy in full-time education mode. Our study focuses on full-time students, as we assume that part-time students have already formed their professional identities, which biases the results. 154 people participated in the study

The table provides an additional specification of the research package.

Study program	Woman	Mans	Total
Undergraduate program	106	10	126
Postgraduate Master's Degree program	33	5	38
Total	138	15	154

As a result of this study, we believe that the following is necessary:

- the need to clearly define the research subject of social pedagogy
- development of working methods and forms of social and educational activities in the field social pedagogy
- clarifying the employability of the social teacher in order to achieve the independent status of this profession;

We also think that the concept of the TAT subject curriculum should be changed in such a way that it can respond to the demands of the labor market (that is, the demands of social services and educational institutions) in a more flexible way. We often hear that graduates are not well-prepared for their jobs. Universities don't complain about students not having enough theoretical knowledge, but they complain

about graduates' lack of personal training and soft skills. Therefore, we decided to expand the research concept.

The program as described in the article: we have added innovative themes. It is very important that students have more internal motivation to develop their abilities and skills, and at the same time, the subjects in the curriculum help to improve their communication skills (openness to communication), which is a constant in today's society. adapts to changing situations. (flexibility) and improving their work orientation (achievement motivation, formation and leadership) remains a challenge.

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